

PRINCIPLES OF JUSTICE IN ISSUING COMMUNITY MINING PERMITS IN INDONESIA

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Abstract

The purpose of this research is to find the essence of granting people's mining permits in Indonesia that are fair for the greatest prosperity of the people, to study and analyze the regulation and implementation of granting people's mining permits, and to find the ideal principles of granting people's mining permits that are fair in Indonesia. This research is a normative legal research that includes a study of the basic principles contained in Pancasila, the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia and other laws and regulations using a philosophical approach, a historical approach, a legislative approach, a conceptual approach, and a comparative approach. The results of this research found that (1) the essence of granting people's mining permits in Indonesia is to realize sustainable ecological justice, justice for economic equality, and social justice. (2) The arrangement of authority between the central and regional governments has so far been centralistic in nature which has created new problems not only for the independence of autonomous regions, but is also vulnerable to corruption in people's mining permits. (3) Thus, in the future, *re-decentralization* needs to be implemented based on social justice, ecology, and economic equality to realize accountability, protection of people around the mine, and people's prosperity.

Keywords: Principle of Justice, Granting of Permits, Community Mining.

INTRODUCTION

The history of serious mining management in Indonesia was marked by the enactment of Law No. 11 of 1967 concerning Basic Provisions on Mining, which was accompanied by the birth of regulations on *investment*, namely Law No. 1 of 1967 concerning Foreign Investment.

Following the reforms in Indonesia in 1998, Law No. 11 of 1967 concerning Basic Provisions on Mining was replaced by Law No. 4 of 2009 concerning Mineral and Coal Mining. This was followed by Law No. 3 of 2020 concerning amendments to Law No. 4 of 2009 concerning Mineral and Coal Mining.

Finally, Law No. 2 of 2025 concerning the Fourth Amendment to Law No. 4 of 2009 concerning Mineral and Coal Mining.

Decentralization of the granting of mining business permits began to be implemented after the enactment of Law No. 4 of 2009.

In this law... It is explained that the granting of mining permits can only be carried out by the Central Government (represented by the KPM); the Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources and the Governor or Regent/Mayor.

Article 37 of Law No. 4 of 2009 states that "Mining Business Permits (IUP)" are granted by:

- a. Regent/mayor if the WIUP is located within one district area;
- b. Governor if the WIUP is located across district/city areas within (one) province after obtaining a recommendation from the local Regent/Mayor in accordance with statutory regulations; and
- c. Minister if the WIUP is located across provincial areas after obtaining recommendations from the local governor and regent/mayor in accordance with statutory regulations

After the change of government regime, mining permit regulations began to experience problems again, which marked by the enactment of Law No. 3 of 2020 as an amendment to Law No. 4 of 2009 concerning Mineral and Coal Mining. The mining licensing problem became more complicated after the enactment of Law No. 2 of 2025 concerning the Fourth Amendment to Law No. 4 of 2009 concerning Mineral and Coal Mining, because the provisions of Law No. 2 of 2025 further strengthen the centralization system, which is emphasized through Article 35 paragraph (1), paragraph (3) and paragraph (4) and paragraph (5). In the provisions of Article 35 paragraph (1) it explains that only the central government has the authority to issue mining permits. Based on these provisions, the authority of regional governments especially the authority of the Regent/Mayor has been automatically revoked in issuing mining permits. Furthermore, Article 35 paragraph (5) of Law No. 2 of 2025 emphasizes that mining permits are implemented online by the central government in an integrated manner, or what is known as *the online single submission (OSS) system*. The implementation of the OSS is also emphasized by the issuance of Government Regulation No. 5 of 2021 concerning the implementation of risk-based licensing, which is an implementing regulation of Law No. 6 of 2023 concerning Job Creation.

With the revocation of the regional government's authority to issue people's mining permits (IPR), this has led to an imbalance of authority between the central and regional governments. Regarding the centralization of natural resource management, it is emphasized based on Article 14 paragraph (1) and paragraph (3) of Law No. 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government, where the essence of the article recommends that the management of marine resources, forestry and natural resources can only be carried out by the Central Government. This provision ultimately leads to inequality in many things, such as the damage to biological natural resources; the occurrence of horizontal conflicts between mining actors and local communities; and the distribution of income between the central and regional governments is uneven for mining results because only the central government receives PNB (Non-Tax State Revenue), while the regions receive nothing. Even though it has been explained in Article 285 paragraph (1) of Law No. 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government, that regional original income includes (1) Taxes; (2) Regional levies; (3) results of managing separated regional assets and (4) other legitimate regional original income.

Philosophically, the centralized mining permit granting *policy is one of the causes of injustice* in Indonesia, because it clearly violates the principle of justice aspired by the founders of this nation, especially contrary to the fifth principle, namely the principle of Social Justice for All

Indonesian People. According to *Rahmat Safaat*, ¹the imbalance in the authority to issue permits in the mining sector between the central and regional governments has resulted in mining business actors and State-Owned Enterprises (BUMN), both from national private elements and from foreign private companies, ignoring the principles of good governance *and* ignoring the principles of good environmental governance, so that indiscriminate natural exploitation activities will continue to occur without limits.

Sociologically, errors in mining permit management can be caused by several factors, including vested interests and greed. Fraud can arise from a lack of control over individual personalities, which can lead to disregard for established moral values, both those enshrined in state law, religious law, and even the moral values embedded in customary law in each region of Indonesia.

Legally Based on Article 35 paragraph (1), paragraph (4) and paragraph (5) of Law No. 2 of 2025 concerning the Fourth Amendment to Law No. 4 of 2009 concerning Minerals and Coal, *the complexity* of mining governance issues appears to be increasingly complicated, which according to several observers, the law is flawed in the process of its creation, because it appears to be full of *collusion, corruption and nepotism* and ignores the principles of good and proper governance *and* ignores the principles of good environmental *governance*, ² Articles contained in Law No. 2 of 2025 expressly recommends that mining permit applications be submitted directly to the central government electronically.

All the convenience of *online* and centralized permit issuance can create increasingly *complex problems*, resulting in negative consequences in the field of issuing mining permits themselves, because it seems that the government is not serious enough in supervising mining activities. This threatens the sustainability of a good environment because of very serious and widespread damage, and this can occur due to the reduction in supervisory authority from the local government which is the holder of the mining permit area, which is a result of the amputation of regional authority in the mining supervision activities.

We can see this in the provisions of Article 177 paragraph (1) of Chapter IV of the Job Creation Law, which gives the obligation only to the central government to supervise mining permits. Thus, the supervisory structure mechanism becomes ineffective because of the long bureaucratic flow that must be gone through due to the very wide span of control from the central government to the regions. ³

Based on the background of the problem, to create conditions for granting mining permits that prioritize the value of social justice and balance between the central and regional governments, appropriate regulations are needed.

In order to create licensing regulations that are socially just and beneficial to all Indonesians, and to further implement regional autonomy as broadly as possible based on the law, it is hoped that harmonious and proportional legal regulations will be established between the central and regional governments. This will enable regions to effectively and responsibly supervise mining activities, particularly those conducted by Recipients of People's Mining Permits (IPR).

METHOD

This research is a normative legal research using a philosophical approach, a historical approach, a legislative approach, and a conceptual approach. The legal materials used in this research are sourced from primary, secondary, and tertiary legal materials. The method of collecting legal materials through literature studies, which then analyzed the obtained legal materials deductively by building arguments based on logical and systematic reasoning. This method allows for accurate and comprehensive solutions to problems related to the reconstruction of the granting of community mining permits that are just and sustainable.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Decentralization of People's Mining Permit Management Based on Law Number 4 of 2009

Regulations on mining within the framework of regional autonomy through the spirit of reform can actually be found at the beginning of the issuance of Government Regulation (PP) Number 75 of 2001. Regarding the Second Amendment to Government Regulation Number 32 of 1969 concerning the Implementation of Law Number 11 of 1967 concerning Basic Provisions on Mining. To accommodate the intent and purpose of Government Regulation (PP) No. 75 of 2001 which in its articles provides the authority of Governors and Regents/Mayors to issue mining permits. On the basis of reform in Indonesia, further with the birth of Law No. 4 of 2009 concerning Mineral and Coal Mining as a replacement for Law Number 11 of 1967, further strengthens the authority of Regents/Mayors in regulating the management of mining permits in Indonesia.

Article 37 of Law No. 4 of 2009 states that "Mining Business Permits (IUP)" are granted by: ⁴

- a) Regent/mayor if the WIUP is located within one district area;
- b) Governor if the WIUP is located across district/city areas within (one) province after obtaining a recommendation from the local Regent/Mayor in accordance with statutory regulations; and
- c) Minister if the WIUP is located across provincial areas after obtaining recommendations from the local governor and regent/mayor in accordance with statutory regulations.

With the authority of the Regent/Mayor according to Law No. 4 of 2009, especially as previously regulated in Article 37 of the law, this authority can be further emphasized with the issuance of the Minister of Energy and Mineral Resources Regulation No. 2 of 2013 concerning Supervision of the Implementation of Mining Business Management Carried Out by Provincial and Regency/City Governments. Article 4 of Law Number 4 of 2009 concerning Mineral and Coal Mining explains that non-renewable minerals and coal are a type of national natural wealth that must be controlled by the state to be used as much as possible for the prosperity of the people. ⁵ Then in the explanation of Article 9 of Law No. 4 of 2009, *that the authority in managing Mineral and Coal mining must be managed by the Government, Provincial Government, Regency/City Government.*

In the explanation of Article 6 letter (e) of Law No. 4 of 2009 concerning Mineral and Coal Mining in the regulation of mining permit areas, the determination of mining areas is part of the national spatial planning which will be determined by the central government after coordination with regional governments and the DPR, with the following provisions;⁶

“(a) Mining business areas that have been determined by the government must first be coordinated with the local government and then submitted in writing to the DPR-RI; (b) People's Mining Areas will be determined by the Regent/Mayor after consulting with the Regional People's Representative Council (DPRD); © State reserve areas will be determined by the government for national strategic interests, reserved for certain commodities, and for conservation areas in order to maintain the balance of the ecosystem and environment.”

One of the most important objectives of the formation of Law Number 4 of 2009 according to Tri Hayati, is that the Law has its own special feature by eliminating all forms of permits in the form of Mining Authorization (KP) and Work Contract (KK) which were inherited by Law Number 11 of 1967. Thus, the birth of Law Number 4 of 2009 concerning Mineral and Coal Mining gave birth to a single form of permit, namely the Mining Business Permit (IUP) within the framework of the broadest possible regional autonomy.⁷

2. Centralization of Community Mining Permit Management Following the Issuance of Law No. 3 of 2020

In general, in the long process of mining permit governance in Indonesia, there has always been a degradation of change in accordance with the mission of the ruling government regime, which was previously centralistic during the New Order era, namely with the issuance of Law Number 11 of 1967 concerning Basic Provisions on Mining.

Based on the spirit of reform that began rolling since 1998, Law No. 11 of 1967 was replaced again with the spirit of *decentralization* within the framework of the broadest possible regional autonomy, which was marked by the issuance of Law Number 4 of 2009 concerning Mineral and Coal Mining, and based on the provisions in Law 32 of 2004 concerning Regional Government.

Then, regarding the regulation of People's Mining Permits (IPR), it was previously regulated in Article 1 number (10) of Law No. 4 of 2009 concerning Mineral and Coal Mining. Explanation of Article 1 number (10) of Law No. 4 of 2009, the term "community mining permit" (IPR) refers to a permit granted for community mining areas with a limited area and limited investment. Similarly, the same explanation is found in the explanation of the sentence. *General Regulation of the Minister of Energy and Mineral Resources (PERMEN) No. 2 of 2013* concerning Supervision of the Implementation of Mining Businesses Implemented by Provincial Governments and Regency/City Governments.

As a form of strategic step in carrying out the mandate of Article 18 paragraph (2) of the 1945 Constitution which is closely related to the balance of authority between the central and regional governments, so that it is very much in sync with the issuance of Law Number 32 of 2004 concerning Regional Government, when connected with the provisions of Article 37 of

Law Number 4 of 2009 concerning Minerals and Coal. However, hopes for the implementation of the broadest possible regional autonomy in the mining sector are increasingly disappearing after the issuance of Number 3 of 2020.

With the enactment of Law No. 3 of 2020 concerning Amendments to Law No. 4 of 2009 concerning Mineral and Coal Mining, and with the enactment of Law No. 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government, which replaces Law No. 32 of 2004 concerning Regional Government, it cannot be denied that there has been another *recentralization* of authority in issuing mining permits. All of this proves that the practice of anomalous justice in issuing mining permits is increasingly evident. Article 35 paragraph (1) of Law No. 3 of 2020 explains that *"the issuance of mining business permits can only be carried out by the central government."*⁸ Then in Article 35 paragraph (4) of the law it explains that "the Central Government can delegate its authority to the Provincial Government in accordance with statutory regulations."

Article 14 paragraph (1) of Law No. 23 of 2014 explains that *"The implementation of government affairs in the fields of forestry, maritime affairs, energy and mineral resources is divided between the central and provincial governments."* Thus, the explanation of Article 14 paragraph (1) means that the implementation of the regional autonomy program in the management of natural resources is only valid up to the provincial level government (by the Governor) on the basis of *delegation* from the central government.⁹

3. Centralization of Mining Licensing Based on Law Number 2 of 2025

Philosophically, in the context of the formation of all regulations regarding mining, the aim is basically to apply the objectives of Article 33 paragraph (3) of the 1945 Constitution, namely that "The land, water and natural resources contained therein are controlled by the state and used as much as possible for the prosperity of the people. In this regard, it is very much in sync with the general explanation of Law No. 2 of 2025 concerning the Fourth Amendment to Law No. 4 of 2009 concerning Mineral and Coal Mining. The explanation emphasizes that Minerals and Coal in the territory of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia are non-renewable natural resources which are gifts from God Almighty. It is explained that the management of natural resources should be controlled by the state fairly in order to increase added value to strengthen the national economy. This aims to realize the prosperity of the people in a socially just manner, as mandated in Article 33 paragraph (3) of the 1945 Constitution"¹⁰

The legal basis for amending the Minerba Law through Law No. 2 of 2025 concerning the Fourth Amendment to Law No. 4 of 2009 concerning Minerals and Coal, was initially inseparable from the Constitutional Court Decision No. 64/PUU-XVIII/2020 which confirmed the annulment of Law No. 11 of 2020 concerning Job Creation, which was decided in a formal review by the Constitutional Court based on Decision Mk. No. 91/PUU-XVIII/2020. Then, the formation of the law was also inseparable from the Constitutional Court Decision No. 37/PUU-XIX/2021. From the Constitutional Court Decision No. 64/PUU-XVIII/2020, it was stated that the Formation of Law No. 11/2020 concerning Job Creation was declared contrary to the 1945 Constitution and did not have conditional binding legal force as long as it was not interpreted

as if no improvements were made within two years, since this decision was pronounced. Therefore, based on that provision, Law No. 2 of 2025 was then enacted.¹¹ As previously explained, at the beginning of the ratification of Law No. 2 of 2025 concerning the Fourth Amendment to Law No. 4 of 2009 concerning Mineral and Coal Mining, one of the objectives was a form of response to the Constitutional Court Decision No. 37/PUU-XIX/2021, namely because previously the implementation of mining permit contracts had been implemented which were considered problematic by many groups regarding recommendations for extension of mining permits which could be carried out automatically, without going through the process of re-applying for the extension of the issuance of the mining permit through administrative procedures.

On that basis, in resolving licensing problems, precisely with the issuance of Law No. 2 of 2025 is a new chapter of many problems that need to be considered in efforts to improve mining administration in Indonesia today, because the problems that need to be resolved in the law are not only about the elimination of automatic contract extensions, but the purpose of establishing the law is more than that, namely to accommodate the interests of the wider community so that equality occurs, so that all people get convenience from the policy.¹²

In Law No. 2 of 2025, concerning the granting of business permits in the mining sector, efforts are made to improve the governance of granting mining permits by prioritizing the granting of mining permits to several forms of business entities owned by the community as citizens, such as business entities in the form of Cooperatives, Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs), and business entities owned by religious community organizations for the benefit of improving the regional economy.

In addition, Law No. 2 of 2025 also recommends several interests for granting Mining Business Permit Areas (WIUP) to State-Owned Enterprises (BUMN); Regional-Owned Enterprises (BUMD); or Private Enterprises; and also granting mining business area permits to universities, taking into account the accreditation held by each university.¹³ From that provision, the field facts that the author found were actually the opposite, the public's hopes were emptied with the birth of Law No. 2 of 2025, because all matters became centralized. In this regard, we can see the regulation in the provisions of Article 35 of Law No. 2 of 2025 concerning the Fourth Amendment to Law No. 4 of 2009 concerning Mineral and Coal Mining, by adding one paragraph, so that it becomes five paragraphs, which previously only had four paragraphs in Law No. 3 of 2020 concerning Amendments to Law No. 4 of 2009 concerning Mineral and Coal Mining.

In full, the provisions of Article 35 of Law No. 2 of 2025 read as follows:¹⁴

" Article (1) mining businesses are carried out based on business permits from the central government; Verse (2) Business licensing as referred to in paragraph 1 is implemented by providing: (a) a business registration number; (b) a standard certificate and/or; © permit. Article (3) The permits referred to in paragraph 2 letter c consist of: IUP, IUPK, IUPK as a continuation of contract/agreement operations, IPR, SIPB, assignment permits, IUJP, and IUP for sales. Article (4) The central government may delegate the authority to grant business

permits as referred to in paragraph 2 to the Provincial Government in accordance with the provisions of laws and regulations. And Article (5) " The granting of business permits as referred to in paragraph (2) and paragraph (3) follows an electronically integrated business permit system managed by the central government in accordance with the provisions of laws and regulations."

If we examine in depth the birth of Law Number 2 of 2025 concerning the Fourth Amendment to Law Number 4 of 2009 concerning Mineral and Coal Mining, it cannot be denied that the law is increasingly *massive* in achieving its objectives by further strengthening the authority of the central government in efforts to regulate mining permits, which are carried out electronically and integrated with the *OSS (Online Single Submission) system*.

The following are some of the core new contents in Law No. 2 of 2025 concerning the Fourth Amendment to Law No. 4 of 2009 concerning Mineral and Coal Mining, including: ¹⁵

1. The issuance of Law No. 2 of 2025 concerning the Fourth Amendment to Law No. 4 of 2009 is a form of adjustment to the implementation of Constitutional Court Decision No. 64 / PUU-XVIII / 2020 and Constitutional Court Decision No. 37 / PUU-XIX / 2021.
2. Regulation of Mining Business Permit Areas (WIUP) for Metal Minerals and Coal is given priority to cooperatives, small and medium enterprises, business entities owned by religious community organizations that carry out economic functions to improve the regional economy.
3. Granting of Mining Business Permit Areas (WIUP) for Metal Minerals, Mining Business Permit Areas (WIUP) for Coal and Special Mining Business Permit Areas (WIUPK) with priority for the interests of Universities, to State-Owned Enterprises (BUMN), Private Enterprises by considering the area of Mining Business Permit Areas (WIUP) for Metal Minerals, Mining Business Permit Areas (WIUP) for Coal or Special Mining Business Permit Areas (WIUPK), by looking at the Accreditation of universities and to improve access and educational services for the community.
4. Mining Business Permit Areas (WIUP) for metal minerals or coal for downstreaming purposes can be granted to State-Owned Enterprises (BUMN) and Private Enterprises on a priority basis.
5. Special Mining Business Permits (IUPK) are granted with priority to State-Owned Enterprises (BUMN), Regionally-Owned Enterprises (BUMD), Cooperatives, Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs), and businesses owned by religious organizations. Meanwhile, Special Mining Business Permits (IUPK) for Private Enterprises are granted through an auction.
6. In order to increase the added value of minerals, this is done by assigning investigations and research to state research institutions, regional research institutions, and private business entities, which are given equal rights in the WIUP or WIUPK mineral auctions.
7. Regulations related to non-tax state revenue (PNBP) obtained in the implementation of Mineral and Coal Mining business activities are managed by the minister.

8. Provisions related to Mining Business Permits (IUP) issued before the enactment of this Law will be reviewed based on central government assessments. If there is any overlap in policies, the WIUP will be revoked and returned to the state.
9. The deadline for the formation of implementing regulations and monitoring and review of this Law shall be after this Law comes into force.

4. Ideal Arrangement of Government Authority in Granting Permits Equitable People's Mining.

The philosophical framework in developing relations between the central and regional governments in the mining sector is a form of support to implement the country's economic needs in order to achieve the objectives of Article 33 and Article 18 of the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia.

The goal is to achieve the greatest possible prosperity for the people, and also to support the protection of healthy and sustainable environmental governance. To achieve the desired social justice, the ideal concept for achieving equitable mining governance, in addition to prioritizing justice in the economic sector, of course also prioritizes long-term goals. In that context, the main thing is to maintain environmental sustainability in order to maintain the relay of the living needs of future generations of the nation in a sustainable manner.

In studying the concept of regional autonomy has a different excitement from studying the concept of legal science in constitutional law in general, because in the topic of regional autonomy the issues that arise are about the dynamics of the problems faced alternately with the changing regulations that regulate the relationship between the central and regional governments through laws on regional governments, laws on the balance of central and regional finances, as well as several laws related to regional governments, such as the Job Creation Law, the Minerba Law, the Forestry Law, the Law on the environment and others.

This matter has recently become a very complex problem after the birth of Law Number 11 of 2020 concerning Job Creation, which was then subject to a material review by the Constitutional Court (MK), so that it was replaced through the issuance of Law Number 6 of 2023 concerning Job Creation.

The aim of implementing the concept of regional autonomy in the mining sector is to be one form of effort to achieve the future vision of managing the mining sector in Indonesia in a sustainable manner in order to achieve justice in the economic sector, justice in the legal sector, justice in environmental management and supervision, and how to design the implementation of the ideal concept in the implementation of granting mining permits that are socially just within the framework of the broadest possible regional autonomy.

The conflicting regulations in the mining sector are inextricably linked to overlapping policies, which have long been believed to be the root cause of the problems. These problems, in their various forms, contribute to the harsh reality we face due to the *disharmony of* authority between the central and regional governments.

If we look back, the legal framework established thus far has essentially been enshrined in the provisions of previous regional government laws and mining laws, which adhere to the principle of *decentralization*. However, there has been a *derivation* related to changes in licensing regulations, as licensing regulations have, on the other hand, been implemented centrally. This derivation of mining regulations through centralized licensing has also been realized in various related laws and regulations, such as those contained in the Mining Law, the Law on Regional Government, the Law on the Environment, the Job Creation Law, and various implementing regulations.

If it is connected with the regulation on mining, it cannot be separated from the provisions outlined in the Law on Mineral and Coal Mining and the Law on Regional Government, in which the law initially recommended that in the power to regulate mining, the state has the authority to issue mining permits within the framework of the broadest possible regional autonomy, through the task of delegating authority to the Governor and Regent/Mayor. The authority of regional governments within the framework of autonomy was previously regulated in Law No. 32 of 2004 concerning Regional Government and in Law No. 4 of 2009 concerning Mineral and Coal Mining. However, these regulations were subsequently reduced through several amendments, which then became the absolute authority of the central government in terms of issuing mining permits through the concept of centralized licensing. The latest changes were made through the issuance of Law No. 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government and based on Law No. 2 of 2025 concerning the Fourth Amendment to Law No. 4 of 2009 concerning Mineral and Coal Mining.

5. Redecentralization in the Regulation of Authority for the Granting of Equitable People's Mining Permits

Following the change in regulations through Law Number 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government and reinforced by Law Number 2 of 2025 by revising Law Number 4 of 2009 concerning Mineral and Coal Mining, the direction of mining licensing policy in Indonesia is moving towards centralization. The Reform Era The authority to grant permits, including People's Mining Permits (IPR) based on Law No. 4 of 2009, was largely at the district/city level, considering the closeness of regional authorities to local conditions and the needs of local communities. However, after the legal reform, this authority was withdrawn to the provinces and ultimately dominated by the central government. Despite the noble goal of the reform, it gave rise to a new discourse regarding the urgency of redcentralization, namely the idea of returning some licensing authority to regional governments, with a more balanced arrangement between the central and regional governments.¹⁶

One of the most prominent problems with centralization is the breakdown in communication between local communities and policymakers at the central level. The aspirations of communities in mining areas are often not fully conveyed due to lengthy and multi-layered bureaucratic processes. For example, proposals for the establishment of People's Mining Areas (WPR) from district governments must go through the provincial government before being approved by the ministry. This process is not only time-consuming but also robs communities of their sense of ownership over policies that affect their livelihoods. As a result, the state's

legitimacy in the eyes of the community is weakened, while illegal mining practices are on the rise as a form of resistance against a bureaucracy perceived as impartial.

On the other hand, centralization also limits the central government's capacity to address artisanal mining issues across Indonesia's vast territory. The geographic conditions, social characteristics, and mining potential vary widely across regions, making them difficult to manage with a unified approach from the center. Regional governments actually possess a comparative advantage in the form of local knowledge, *which allows them to better respond to regional dynamics. However, when regional authority is narrowed, this potential is neglected, and policies often fall short of the actual needs* of local communities. From this perspective, *decentralization* offers a solution to restore the role of regions without diminishing the central government's coordinating role.

Re - decentralization does not mean a return to the past when regions had full authority without adequate control from the central government. Instead, redcentralization is intended as a fairer and more effective redistribution of authority: the central government establishes norms, standards, procedures, and criteria (NSPK), while the technical implementation of IPR grants is returned to provincial or even district/city governments, which are closer to the people. This model not only shortens the bureaucratic chain but also allows for a faster response to community mining issues, including land disputes, conflicts with IUP/IUPK holders, IPRs, and environmental issues, which are often local in nature.¹⁷

Experiences in various countries show that controlled decentralization of mining authority actually increases governance effectiveness. For example, in the Philippines, local governments are given the role of determining small-scale mining areas with oversight from the central government, resulting in a more participatory licensing mechanism. Similarly, in several African countries, such as Ghana, a community-based model for granting permits for artisanal mining with central supervision is considered more effective in reducing illegal mining practices.¹⁸ These practices demonstrate that redcentralization, when well-designed, can reconcile the need for state control with the interests of local communities.

Redcentralization is not without risks. The potential for practical Corruption, collusion, and nepotism in the regions remain a serious threat. The institutional design of redcentralization must be accompanied by strict accountability mechanisms, including digital technology-based oversight and civil society involvement. Furthermore, the central government must retain its authority in establishing NSPK (National Mining Standards) and its macro-oversight function, ensuring that licensing practices in the regions do not conflict with national interests and environmental sustainability principles. With this institutional design, redcentralization can actually improve the overall quality of mining governance.¹⁹

Finally, *decentralization* in the granting of People's Mining Permits (IPR) must be viewed not merely as an issue of government administration, but as a concrete manifestation of the implementation of the principles of social justice and economic democracy as mandated by the constitution. *By* returning some authority to the regions, the state recognizes the strategic role of local communities in resource management, while simultaneously strengthening the state's

legitimacy in the eyes of the people. ²⁰ *Re - decentralization* is thus not only about the distribution of authority, but about bringing substantive justice to the management of natural resources, so that IPR truly becomes an instrument of people's welfare, not just a legal formality.

The paradigm shift in licensing management in Indonesia, which is centralized, has become a paradox in the interpretation of the authority to grant mining permits, due to overlapping policies between higher-level regulations and lower-level regulations, which are then followed by policies at the government level that are also not in sync with the relevant laws related to the intent of the policy. For example, the conflict occurs between Law Number 4 of 2009 concerning Mineral and Coal Mining and Law Number 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government, as well as its implementing regulations.

The mining regulations in both laws were previously decentralized, which then changed to a centralized regulation after the enactment of the Job Creation Law, namely Law Number 6 of 2023. Then, this centralization was emphasized with the issuance of implementing regulations of the Job Creation Law, with the enactment of Government Regulation (PP) No. 5 of 2021 concerning the Implementation of Risk-Based Business Licensing, through the *Online Single Submission (OSS) system*. Therefore, this provision eliminates the authority of regional governments, especially regencies/cities, to manage business licensing. Furthermore, the regulation of mining licensing is also the authority of the central government.

Since the enactment of Law Number 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government as a replacement for Law Number 32 of 2004 concerning Regional Government, there have been significant changes related to natural resource management affairs, which include the regulation of forestry, maritime and mining resources. Article 14 paragraph (1) of Law Number 23 of 2014 explains that *"The implementation of government affairs in the fields of forestry, maritime affairs and energy and mineral resources is divided between the Central Government and the Provincial Government."* This is then emphasized in Article 14 paragraph (3) of Law Number 23 of 2014, which reads *"Government affairs in the field of energy and mineral resources as referred to in paragraph (1) relating to the management of oil and natural gas are the authority of the central government."*

With the central government taking over regional government authority in mining management, the role of districts/cities in managing or supervising mining activities in the event of violations related to licensing is significantly weakened. Consequently, if conflicts of interest arise in mining exploitation cases, they become quite difficult to resolve.

The principle of balance in the management of natural resources, especially in the mining sector, requires attention to how to properly regulate the relationship between the central government, regional governments, and elements within the community. As we understand that the state is a complete system or entity, then related to the management of natural resources, which also includes mineral and coal deposits that belong to the state, and also belong to the local region, namely the province and district/city where the natural resources are located. ²¹

CONCLUSION

The current arrangement of authority between the central and regional governments through Law No. 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government, Law No. 3 of 2020 concerning amendments to Law No. 4 of 2009 concerning Minerals and Coal, by revoking the validity of Law No. 32 of 2004, Law No. 6 of 2023 concerning Job Creation, and Law No. 2 of 2025 concerning the Fourth Amendment to Law No. 4 of 2009 concerning Minerals and Coal, still has a centralistic character that creates new problems not only for the independence of autonomous regions, but is also vulnerable to corruption in people's mining permits. Thus, in the future, *re-decentralization* needs to be implemented based on social justice, ecology, and economic equality to realize accountability, protection of people around the mine, and people's prosperity. With the concept of re-decentralization, mining permits can be fully implemented based on ecological justice and economic justice, and the concept of re-decentralization will fulfill economic justice, balance between central and regional economies, empower local economies, protection of the people around the mine will run well, transparency and public participation, and sustainable intergenerational justice will be achieved.

Footnote

- 1) Rahmat Safaat, *Rekonstruksi Politik Hukum Tata Kelola Pertambangan Mineral dan Batu Bara Berbasis Keadilan Sosial dan Keberlanjutan Lingkungan. Pidato Pengukuhan Guru Besar*, Universitas Brawijaya, Malang, 2020. Hlm. 9
- 2) Rahmat Safaat, *Op.Cit*, hlm. 26-27
- 3) Lihat ketentuan Pasal 177 ayat (1) Pada Bab IV Undang-Undang No. 6 Tahun 2023 tentang Cipta Kerja
- 4) Pasal 37 UU Nomor 4 Tahun 2009
- 5) Pasal 4 Undang-Undang No. 4 Tahun 2009
- 6) Pasal 1 Angka (10) dan Pasal 6 Huruf (e) Undang-Undang Nomor 4 Tahun 2009
- 7) Tri Hayati, *Op.Cit*, hlm. 85
- 8) Ketentuan dalam Pasal 35 ayat (1) dan Ayat (4) Undang-Undang Nomor 3 Tahun 2020. Dalam pasal 35 tersebut secara terang benderang telah menghapus segala kewenangan Bupati/Walikota dalam menerbitkan izin pertambangan.
- 9) Pasal 14 ayat (1) Undang-Undang No. 23 Tahun 2014
- 10) Penjelasan Umum UU No. 2 Tahun 2025, hlm. 1
- 11) Ikhtisar Putusan Mahkamah Konstitusi Nomor 37/PUU-XIX/2021
- 12) Putusan Mahkamah Konstitusi Nomor 37/PUU-XIX/2022, tanggal 29 September Tahun 2022. Bahwa Putusan MK tersebut menurut tim advokasi UU Minerba yang mewakili hak-hak rakyat dalam melakukan advokasi atas uji materi UU minerba menyebutkan bahwa Keputusan MK tersebut justru memperkokoh kepentingan oligarki tambang, dan sekaligus menghancurkan keselamatan rakyat. Sumber: *walhi.or.id*, diakses tanggal 11 mei 2025
- 13) Ketentuan Pasal 51 Undang-Undang no. 2 Tahun 2025.
- 14) Ketentuan Pasal 35 UU No. 2 Tahun 2025
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